

Genetic diversity of sweet potato (*ipomoea batatas* L.) of Central Java based on morphological character

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ABSTRACT

The yard is one place to preserve the diversity of genetic resources plants and traditional (local) varieties. Therefore it needs to be inventoried and characterized in order to protect, utilize and develop the diversity of local plant both in-situ and ex-situ in the provision of diverse food. The study was conducted at KP Bandongan, on 12 accessions of sweet potato collected from various regions. Observation of phenotypic characters was carried out during vegetative and generative growth by using the sweet potato characterization guide. The results of dendrogram based on the morphological character of 14 sweet potato cultivars showed that the similarity of 10.36% was divided into 2 groups, where cultivar number 4 was separated from other cultivars. The closest similarity was in nos. 2 and 6, while nos. 12 and 13 were 40.24% and 41.75%, respectively. These results indicate that 14 cultivars were characterized on high diversity.

Keywords : genetic diversity, sweet potato, Central Java

INTRODUCTION

Sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* L.) is among the world's most important, versatile and underutilized foodcrops grown generally for its storage roots (Tortoe, 2010).It is a hexaploid ($2n=6x=90$), dicotyledonous root-tuber crop belonging to the family Convolvulaceae (Austin and Huaman, 1996). The colour of the stem and leaves varies from green to purple due to anthocyanin pigmentation (Laurie and Niederwieser, 2004). The texture, sweetness, size and shape of the tubers vary with different varieties. It is a shortcycle crop which usually matures in (3-4) months (Anyaeibunam et al., 2008) and may be grown two or threetimes in a year (Okonkwo, 2002).

Among the tuber crops grown in the world, sweet potato ranks second after cassava (Ray and Ravi, 2005). China accounts for the highest sweet potato production in the world, followed by Uganda and Nigeria (FAO, 2011). The area under sweet potato production in Nigeria is estimated at about 204.7 million hectares of land with 2.516 million metric tons of sweet potato in 2005 and 3.462 million metric tons in 2006 (Srinivas, 2009, Anyaeibunam et al., 2008). These

increases were attributed to improved technological inputs, international and national research efforts (Anyaegebunam et al., 2008). Yields vary greatly according to cultivars, local climatic conditions and cultural techniques (Antiaobong, 2007).

Generally, yields in farmer's plots are low (Njoku et al., 2009) due to the use of local genotypes but could be increased with use of improved varieties (Nwankwo et al., 2012). The crop can be considered very important in promoting nutritional security particularly in agriculturally backward areas (Srinivas, 2009) with poor soils.

Sweet potato has gained importance in the recent years in some states of Indonesia, due to declining productivity of food grains and extensive loss of crops due to frequent disasters. In this context, sweet potato is viewed as an alternate food crop due to its ability to survive in harsh environment, high production potential, cheap nutrient supply and wide adaptability to varied climatic conditions there by meeting food requirements of majority of the disadvantaged population especially in the off season (Sivakumar, 2003). Thus, it has been widely used for food and industrial application. In rural areas, the limited transport infrastructure has encouraged small-scale local processing and the development of household-based feed (Marter and Timmins, 1992). Therefore, the objective is to study the morphological diversity of the cultivars during its growth, development and harvesting stage, and to determine the morphological characteristics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Bandungan, 14 accessions of sweet potatoes collected from various regions (Table 1). Vine cuttings were sown during middle of November at a spacing of 60 x 20 cm in well pulverized raised bed. Well rotten farm yard manure @ 25 ton/ha was applied at the time of field preparation as basal dressing (10 days before planting) and mixed well with the soil. The recommended fertilizer dose was 20:40:60 kg NPK/ha as basal and 20:40:60 kg NPK/ha after 30 days. Urea, single super phosphate and muriate of potash were used as a source of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, respectively.

First irrigation was given immediately after planting. Then the subsequent irrigations were given at an interval of 10-15 days depending upon the soil moisture and weather condition. Sweet potato was harvested 120 days after planting when leaves turn yellow and shed. The crop was irrigated 4-6 days prior to harvest to facilitate harvesting. Morphological characters such as length (main vine), number of shoots and leaves per plant during growth and development; tuber characters (skin and flesh colors, shape, weight, length,

girth, number and yield per plant) after harvesting were recorded following standard description after 120 days growth period.

Observation of phenotypic characters was carried out during vegetative and generative growth, in accordance with plant growth stadia using Descriptor for Sweet Potato (CIP, AVRDC, and IBPGR, 1991).

Table1. Sweet potato accessions characterized in 2015

No.	Kode	Local Name	Origin area
1	UJ-jtg-16	Ungu	Banjarnegara
2	UJ-jtg-28	Royan	Jepara
3	UJ-jtg-48	Jepang/48	Karanganyar
4	UJ-jtg-40	Rami/40	Karanganyar
5	UJ-jtg-44	Rempyok	Karanganyar
6	UJ-jtg-21	Merah	Banjarnegara
7	UJ-jtg-17	Kuning	Banjarnegara
8	UJ-jtg-43	Sanggan/43	Karanganyar
9	UJ-jtg-54	Genjah/54	Karanganyar
10	UJ-jtg-42	Kolakan/42	Karanganyar
11	UJ-jtg-41	Korea/41	Karanganyar
12	UJ-jtg-10	Buahungu/10	Banjarnegara
13	UJ-jtg-52	Korea/52	Karanganyar
14	UJ-jtg-53	Mangul	Semarang

Characterization results were analyzed by genetic relationship analysis based on morphological characteristics observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tuber yield of the sweet potato cultivars show multiple positive correlations with their morphological characters like plant length, leaf and shoot number, and the tuber characteristics like tuber length, number, girth and weight (Reddy et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Leaf characteristics, skin color and shape, as well as the color of tuber meat for 14 local Central Java sweet potato accessions

Figure 2. Dendrograms of 14 local sweet potato cultivars based on morphological characters

The results of dendrogram based on the morphological characters of 14 sweet potato cultivars characterized (Figure 2) showed that the similarity of 10.36% was divided into 2 groups, where cultivar number 4 was separated from other cultivars. Cultivars that have the closest similarity are in nos. 2 and 6, and nos. 12 and 13 showed similarity levels of 40.24% and 41.75% respectively. These results indicate that of the 14 cultivars characterized by high diversity. Research on the diversity and relationship of wild sweet potato relatives has

also been carried out by Setiawati et al., 2015 the results show that there is a high genetic diversity from accessions studied and can be used as a reference in crossing to assemble new varieties and enrich genetic diversity.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of dendrogram based on the morphological characters of 14 sweet potato cultivars characterized showed that the similarity of 10.36% was divided into 2 groups. Sweet potato is viewed as an alternate food crop due to its ability to survive in harsh environment, high production potential, cheap nutrients supply and wide adaptability to varied climatic conditions thereby meeting food requirements of majority of the disadvantaged population especially in the offseason.

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REFERENCES

- Antiaobong, E.E. 2007. Life cycle, economic threshold and control of Sweet potato weevils, *Cylaspuncticollis* Boh (Coleoptera:Curculionidae) in Akwalbom State, Nigeria. Ph.D Thesis submitted to Michael Okpara University of Agriculture. Umudike- Nigeria, pp. 3 –5.
- Anyaegbunam, H. N, Asumugha G. N., Mbanasor E.O., Ezulike T.O. and Nwosu K.I. 2008. Guide to Improved sweet Potato Production in Nigeria. National Root Crops Research Institute, Umudike, Extension Guide. 24: 1-9.
- Austin, D. F. and Huaman Z. 1996. A synopsis of *Ipomoea* (Convolvulaceae). In: The Americas Taxon. 45:3–38.
- CIP, AVRDC, and IBPGR. 1991. *Descriptor for Sweet Potato*. Z. Huaman (ed.). Internatipnal Board for Plant Genetic Resources, Rome, Italy.
- FAO. 2011. Food and Agricultural Statistical Database Available from; <http://faostat.fao.org>.
- Laurie, S.M. and Niederwieser J.G. 2004. The Sweet potato plant. In Niederwieser, J. G. (ed.) Guide to Sweet potato production in South Africa. *Agri. Res. Council.*, 1:7-14.

- Marter, A.D. and Timmins W.H. 1992. Small scale processing of sweet potato in sichuan province, P. R. China. *Tropical Science.*, **32**:241-250.
- Njoku, J.C, Muoneke C.O., Okocha P.I. and Ekeleme F. 2009. Effect of propagule size and intra-row spacing on the growth and yield of Sweet potato in a humid agro-ecological zone. *Nigerian Agri. J.* **40**(1): 115-124.
- Nwankwo, I.I.M., Bassey E.E., Afuape S.O., Njoku J, Korieocha D.S., Nwaigwe, G and Echendu T.N.C. 2012. Morpho-Agronomic characterization and evaluation of in-country sweet potato accessions in south-eastern Nigeria. *J. Agri. Sci.*, **4**(11): 281-288.
- Okonkwo, J. C. 2002. Effect of time of introducing Soybean into Potato on the performance of Potato/Soybean intercrop in Jos Plateau, Nigeria. *J. Sust. Agri. Envt.*, **4**(2): 185-191.
- Ray, R.C. and Ravi V. 2005. Post-harvest spoilage of sweet potato and its control measures. *Critical Review of Food Sci. Nutr.*, **35**: 623-644.
- Reddy, R., H. Soibam, V. S. Ayam, P. Panja and S. Mitra. Morphological characterization of sweet potato cultivars during growth, development and harvesting. *Indian J. Agric. Res.*, **52** (1) 2018 : 46-50.
- Setiawati, T. Karyono, T. Supriatundan A. Karuniawan. 2015. Estimasi Kergamandan Kekeabatan 60 akses Kerabat Liar Ubi Jalar Berdasarkan Karakter Morfologi. Online: <http://pustaka.unpad.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/12-Estimasi-Keragaman-dan-Kekeabatan.pdf>.
- Sivakumar, P.S. 2003. Sweet potato: A crops for food and nutritional security in Orissa. *Orissa Review*. Pp. 61-64.
- Srinivas, T. 2009. Economics of sweet potato production and marketing, in: Loebenstein, G and Thottapilly, G (Eds.). *The sweet potato*, Spring Science Business Media, BV 2009, 436447.
- Tortoe, C. 2010. Microbial deterioration of white variety Sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* L.) under different storage structures. *Inter.J. Plant Bio.* **1**(1):10-15.